

Screening for resistance to bacterial blight of rice under rapid generation advance

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No effective or economical chemical control measures are available so far for bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson, one of the most serious rice diseases in Asia. The use of resistant cultivars seems to be the most efficient and economical control measure.

The feasibility of screening rices resistant to BB in rapid generation

advance (RGA) facilities at IRRI was determined using 43-day-old seedlings of IR28, IR1545-339-2-2, and CH1039.

Two strains of BB — PXO 61 and PXO 86 — were used for inoculation. IR28 is resistant to PXO 61 but susceptible to PXO 86, IR1545-339-2-2 is resistant to both strains, and CH1039 is susceptible to both.

The BB suspension, applied by the clipping technique, contained 10^0 , 10^{-1} , and 10^{-2} cells/ml.

The plants were grown in a shallow box ($55 \times 40 \times 9$ cm) in the RGA facilities. Nitrogen levels were 0, 2, and 4 g ammonium sulfate/week per box from 7 days after germination.

As expected, IR1545-339-2-2 was resistant to all levels of PXO 61 and PXO 86 irrespective of nitrogen levels, while CH1039 showed susceptibility to all concentrations of both strains (see

table). IR28 showed resistance to PXO 61 as expected, but failed to show severe lesion development when inoculated with PXO 86 strain, especially at low nitrogen levels. This could be due to several factors including the depressed growth of the variety.

Irrespective of nitrogen application, lesion development increased with the increased concentration of strains. Strain PXO 61, on the average, showed smaller lesions than did PXO 86. Of all the concentrations, 10^0 cells/ml seemed to be the most effective for lesion development.

The results showed very little delay in flowering as a result of nitrogen level or inoculation by BB. Screening rices resistant to BB seems feasible under RGA. ■

Length of lesions caused by 2 strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* at 3 concentrations of inoculum on 3 rices grown under RGA conditions. IRRI, 1980.

Nitrogen level ^a	Variety or line	PXO 61					PXO 86				
		Av lesion length (cm)				Expected reaction	Av lesion length (cm)				Expected reaction
		10^0	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	Mean		10^0	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	Mean	
0	IR28	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3	R	2.8	2.9	2.8	2.8	S
	IR1545-339-2-2	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3	R	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.3	R
	CH1039	14.8	11.6	9.1	11.8	S	13.4	9.6	8.7	10.6	S
	Mean	5.8	4.7	3.8	4.8		5.9	4.6	4.3	4.9	
2	IR28	1.5	1.4	1.2	1.4	R	4.7	4.6	3.5	4.3	S
	IR1545-339-2-2	1.5	1.3	1.3	1.4	R	1.7	1.7	1.4	1.6	R
	CH1039	15.5	16.7	10.3	14.2	S	17.8	18.7	13.8	16.8	S
	Mean	6.2	6.5	4.3	5.7		8.1	8.3	6.2	7.6	
4	IR28	1.7	1.4	1.2	1.4	R	6.0	5.5	4.9	5.5	S
	IR1545-339-2-2	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.3	R	2.3	1.7	1.5	1.8	R
	CH1039	17.5	16.3	16.0	16.6	S	19.2	18.3	17.5	18.3	S
	Mean	6.9	6.3	6.1	6.4		9.2	8.5	8.0	8.5	

^a0, 2, 4 grams ammonium sulfate/box per week.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Screening for brown planthopper resistance

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Two hundred and four cultivars from AICRIP and IRRI were field-tested for

resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in a randomized replicated trial at the AICRIP center, Aduthurai, in kuruvai 1978. The planting time was adjusted so that BPH infestation was high at flowering. For each variety 2 rows of 17 hills, 1 seedling/hill, were planted. The susceptible checks TN1 and Jaya were planted as skip rows after every 10 cultivars, and 8 rows of Jaya were

planted 1 month earlier around the test varieties. The border rows of Jaya were sprayed with 0.02% methyl parathion at 10-day intervals to encourage BPH buildup. Estimates of BPH damage were made on 2 dates about 1 week apart during peak BPH infestation; 5 plants/row of each cultivar were evaluated.

No cultivar was immune to BPH attack, but 11 showed some field